

solid was filtered off, washed with acetonitrile to remove triethylamine hydrochloride (when benzene was used as a solvent, the mixture was stirred mechanically for ~48 hr, both triethylamine hydrochloride and the compound were precipitated, from which the former was removed by repeated washing with acetonitrile). Yellow crystalline compounds were obtained in both the cases which were found identical in their ir spectra and elemental analysis. The compound was insoluble in almost all organic solvents. It did not melt below 315° but turned dark on heating.

Its composition corresponded to $(C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$. (Found : C, 67.1 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 5.45 ; Ti, 9.8. $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$ requires C, 67.4 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 5.6 ; Ti, 9.64%).

Results and Discussion

The nmr spectrum of *bis*(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)-N-oxido-8-quinolinolate titanium chloride, $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)TiCl$, taken in $CDCl_3$ exhibits two types of protons belonging to quinoline ring protons at δ 7.2-7.3 ppm and the others due to cyclopentadienyl ring protons at δ 6.55 ppm in the ratio of 3 : 5. This confirmed the presence of two cyclopentadienyl rings and one N-oxido-8-quinolinolate group in the molecule. As $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)_2Ti$ is insoluble in $CDCl_3$, its nmr spectrum could not be recorded.

The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} in KBr pellets. The presence of cyclopentadienyl group⁵ is indicated by a C-H stretching at 3040 cm^{-1} , a C-H in plane bending at 1105 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} and C-C stretching at 1430 cm^{-1} and the quinoline ring⁶ by sharp bands at 1570, 1500, 1380 and 1350 cm^{-1} , in both the compounds.

On complexation of heterocyclic N-oxides with metals, the N-O stretching and N-O bending modes are affected^{7,8}. However, in the case of quinoline-N-oxide the N-O stretching band shifts to higher frequencies in 3d metal complexes ; this may be attributed to the impurity of N-O stretching band and an extensive metal to ligand π -bonding^{9,10}. In the present complexes of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide, the N-O stretching is shown by a sharp band at 1310 cm^{-1} as is shown by the free ligand¹¹.

A doublet in the free ligand at 885-875 cm^{-1} has been inferred to be due to N-O bending modes coupled with δ -OH in-plane bending¹². In the spectra of all these complexes, a broad band in the region 950-800 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 840 cm^{-1} and a maximum at 820 cm^{-1} is observed. Since the sharp band at 820 cm^{-1} is due to C-H out-of-plane bending the shoulder at 840 cm^{-1} may be due to N-O bending.

In the far ir region, a band of medium intensity is observed at 350 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2(C_9H_8O_2N)TiCl$, which may be due to Ti-Cl stretching¹³. In the spectra of both the complexes,

two bands of medium intensity are observed at 520-500 cm^{-1} and ~400 cm^{-1} region. These may be due to Ti-O stretching at Ti-O-C and Ti-O-N sites, respectively, as have also been observed in metal-8-quinolinolates¹⁴ at 540-510 cm^{-1} , metal-N-oxido-quinolinolate¹² at ~530 cm^{-1} and metal chelates of aromatic amine oxides^{15,16} at ~440 cm^{-1} .

The observation of two Ti-O stretching bands in the complexes suggest that 8-quinoline-N-oxide acts as a bidentate ligand in N-oxido-8-quinolinolate complexes of titanium reported here.

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Formation Constants of Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} Complexes of N-4-Acylac-naphthylidene-*o*-Aminophenol

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THE successive stability constants of the complexes of N-4-acylacnaphthylidene-*o*-aminophenol with various trivalent metal ions have been determined at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and 0.1 *M* ionic strength and are reported in this communication. The order of stabilities of

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NOTES

metal chelates was found to be $\text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+} < \text{Gd}^{3+} < \text{Dy}^{3+}$.

Experimental

The ligand, N-4-acylacenaphthylidene-o-aminophenol (I), was synthesized and identified as reported earlier^{1,2}. Rare earth chlorides, either taken directly (PrCl_3 , NdCl_3 or DyCl_3) or obtained from oxides (Sm_2O_3 or Gd_2O_3) were made anhydrous³. Appropriate amounts of these rare earth chlorides were dissolved in perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of these ions. The solution of ligand was prepared in ethanol. NaOH (B.D.H.), NaClO_4 (Riedel) and HClO_4 (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in CO_2 free double distilled water. NaOH and HClO_4 solutions were standardised by standard method⁴.

A Philips pH-meter, PP 9040 fitted with combination electrode single rod assembly PV 9014 (accuracy 0.1 pH) was used for pH measurement. The apparatus was standardised against 0.05 M potassium hydrogenphthalate for pH 4 in 80% (v/v) aq. ethanol medium at 30 ± 1 . The pH titrations of the following mixtures were performed against 0.1 M NaOH at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ maintaining the ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4) and total volume 50 ml.

- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 40 ml water.
- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 25 ml (0.005 M) ligand + 15 ml water.
- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 25 ml (0.005 M) ligand + 5 ml metal (0.005 M) + 10 ml water.

The ratio of metal reagent concentration was kept at 1 : 5 to satisfy the highest coordination number of the metal. The above three mixtures were titrated separately adding NaOH progressively with constant stirring (magnetic stirrer) and the pH values were recorded.

Results and Discussion

The ligand being monoprotic, neutralizes one equivalent of base to give one buffer region in its titration curve. Values of formation function $\bar{n}A$ (the average number of protons attached per ligand molecule), \bar{n} (the average number of ligand ions attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent) were calculated using the Irving and Rossotti equations⁵. The protonation constant of the ligand ($\log K_1^H$) and stepwise stability constant of metal-ligand, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated using the half integral method, least square method and pointwise calculation method. The values are

in good agreement with each other and the average values are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

	Temp. $30 \pm 1^\circ$					
	$\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4)					
	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Sm^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	9.68	6.40	6.53	7.05	7.13	7.35
$\log K_2$	—	6.14	6.97	6.70	6.78	7.21

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH , while for the metal ions K_1 and K_2 corresponds to the species ML and ML_2 , respectively.

The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ion was negligible was between 1.5 and 2.0. This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to $\text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+} < \text{Gd}^{3+} < \text{Dy}^{3+}$. The increase in stabilities of rare earth metal complexes with decrease in ionic or crystal radii indicates the absence of extensive covalent bonding due to non-availability of 4f electrons for bond formation.

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Stability Constants of N-4-Methylphenacylidene-anthranilic Acid Complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}

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ACID dissociation constant of N-4-methylphenacylidene-anthranilic acid and the stability constants of its metal chelates with various bivalent metal ions have been determined in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4) by adopting the pH titration technique of Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants follow the Irving-William's order.

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